

PERCEIVED IMPACT OF ENGAGEMENT WITH COMMUNITY SERVICE ON STUDENTS' LEARNING AND DEVELOPMENT TOWARD ACHIEVING SCHOOL'S PHILOSOPHY

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the impact of engagement with community service on students' learning and development toward achieving the school's philosophy of total development of man based on faith, science, and virtue. A descriptive survey research design was utilized involving 229 college students who graduated in 2019 and 2023. The data was gathered through a survey questionnaire. Statistical tools such as frequency, percentage, rank, and mean were used to analyze and present the data. Results of the study reveal that the college students of RCC are mostly engaged in community service activities in terms of social and cultural, education and values formation, health and sanitation, environment and cleanliness, and sports and recreation while they are less engaged in community organization, livelihood, and research. The students strongly agree that their engagement with community service activities opens their eyes to the conditions of people in society, they gain a better understanding of the needs of others, they realize that they are more blessed than others, they are inspired and motivated to continuously improve their life, and they gain a better understanding of people. Through the students' engagement with community service activities, their development based on faith, science, and virtue is achieved to a very great extent. This demonstrates their characteristics as true RCCians. The result implies that the engagement of the college students of RCC with community service activities should be strengthened and sustained to continuously develop well-rounded graduates imbued with the values of faith, science, and virtue.

Keywords: *community service engagement, philosophy, service learning*

INTRODUCTION

The RCC has had an unwavering determination to give quality and purposeful education for more than 77 years. It has provided quality education and services responsive to the changing local and global needs of the students guided by the founder's philosophy of "total development of man based on faith, science, and virtue" (RCC College Student Handbook, 2017).

The term "philosophy" plays a significant role in the lives of the students and the institution itself. In fact, as per Yazıcı (2016), philosophy has different definitions as there are various philosophers from the viewpoints of distinct periods. It is difficult to accurately define its meaning (Heimsoeth, 2011, as cited in Alemdar & Aytaç, 2022). On the other hand, focusing on the literal meaning of philosophy, Cox (2014) argued that it is defined as "love of wisdom," supported by Sönmez (2019) who defined philosophy as "seeking wisdom" for the two words *philo* and *sophia* is the Greek term for love and wisdom.

An institution's philosophy shapes its vision, mission, goals, and objectives. In a study made by Gezer (2018), it was stated that it shapes the teachers' and students' beliefs, experiences, and learning similar to their attitudes toward community service engagement.

Most higher education institutions associate student engagement in community service with vital importance in student learning (Carlisle et al., 2020; Dienhart et al., 2016; Hlalele et al., 2015; Pak, 2020; Zilvinskis et al., 2017). Educational institutions have focused their curriculum on having diverse programs for the community and thus producing a graduate who is highly engaged and has civic-minded characteristics in community service (Afzal & Hussain, 2020). The integration of community engagement in the curriculum benefits the students' fundamental skills in the community and world as a whole – serving to learn and learning to serve.

Given the importance of engagement of students with community service activities, several authors cited that it deepens the awareness of civic responsibility (Bingle & Hatcher, 1995, as cited in Carlisle et al., 2020), improves social skills and community awareness (Eyler & Giles, 1999, as cited in Afzal & Hussain, 2020), enhances social connectedness (Kingston et al., 2014; Kulesza et al., 2022), and strengthen the understanding in subject matter or course content (Mahoney & Schamber, 2011, as cited in Kingston et al., 2014; Smith, 2021), which led to improved academic performance of the students (Afzal & Hussain, 2020; Parlier et al., 2022; Wood & Harris, 2015).

In consideration of community engagement in students' learning, Shumer (2017) mentioned that authentic learning or real education transpires from the experience created and that life is interconnected with the process of community. In addition, applying what students have learned in serving the community goes beyond the simple application of a certain concept in school, it is connected to the experience of others.

Previous studies on the impact of engagement with community service on the student's learning and experiences were conducted and multiple approaches were used to identify the positive and negative factors of the variables.

To determine the service-learning approach to meaningful learning outcomes in a practice profession, Smith (2021) conducted a study on fourteen students who took part in the convergent-mixed methods study. The result implies that there is a positive adjustment to the perspectives of the participants through the community engagement experience. A deeper learning about community service and applying the skills and theory contributed to the adjustment of perspectives.

Likewise, Parlier et al. (2022) investigated the correlation between community service participation and the learning that the participants obtained in purposeful community service activities from the Community College Survey of Student Engagement (CCSSE) with a total of 107,000 respondents coming from 694 institutions. As per the researchers' findings, community service learning and experience are significantly related to community service engagements with the interaction of the teachers and active collaboration activities.

Similarly, Pak (2020) aimed to determine the long-term benefits of community service learning on Spanish students who engaged in different levels of Spanish courses and recognized the aspects of their community service learning and experience. The findings of the research reveal that students' academic and community service learning and experience present a positive outcome and attitudes toward communicating with the target language in communities. It led to positive attainment of the knowledge, attitude, and behavior of the participants. The majority also noted that the community service-learning participation was the notable educational and community involvement they had in college.

To negate previous studies, Dienhart et al. (2016) studied the impacts of mandatory service on students in service-learning classes where the results revealed that participants' initiative and motivation lessened as the external incentive process took place. The impact of community service-learning activities declined as it was a form of requirement for graduation.

The RCC is one of the higher educational institutions that encourages the participation of students in different community service activities. Through engagement with community service activities, the school aims to attain the "The total development of man based on Faith, Science, and Virtue" which is the philosophy – the RCC is lived up to. She professes her noble commitment to developing an integral person whose head, heart, and action are congruent through a well-rounded education. An education that emphasizes not only the intellectual but also the physical, social, emotional, and moral/spiritual development of man is summed up in Faith, Science, and Virtue (RCC College Student Handbook, 2017).

The Faith, Science, and Virtue in the context of the statement in the RCC philosophy, “*Faith* refers to our belief in the existence of a just and loving God. We believe that faith in God gives meaning and purpose to human life. Faith also means belief in our teachers, and their capability to facilitate learning and to bring out the best in our students. We likewise believe in ourselves, in our ability to learn and imbibe knowledge, in our inherent goodness as persons, and therefore, in our ability to live moral lives. *Science* refers to our constant search for knowledge and pursuit of academic excellence through scientific processes, well-planned curricula, efficient and effective instruction and support services, and research. *Virtue* refers to our conviction that since we are inherently good, we can develop moral values through strong determination and perseverance” (RCC College Student Handbook, 2017).

With this philosophy in mind, several activities and requirements are given to the students throughout their educational journey that will contribute to their total development as a person. Among these requirements is students’ engagement with community service (RCC College Student Handbook, 2017).

The RCC Community Extension Service Office (CESO) is an office in charge of monitoring the community service activities of the students. This office is also established to provide opportunities for the members of the RCC to exemplify the spirit of concern in bringing assistance to the underprivileged community through outreach programs and activities (CESO Manual, 2017). Through the community service requirement, students who are the predominant members of the school serve as the main partners of the RCC-CESO in conducting community extension programs ranging from community organization, health and sanitation, education and values formation, livelihood, social and cultural, environment and cleanliness, sports and recreation, and research. This strategy is supported by Braverman et al. (2014) who pointed out that extension programs and undergraduate students are naturally suited to each other in many respects, and getting students involved with extension activities can provide mutual benefits for both the programs and students’ educational development. Many undergraduates are eager to spend some of their educational time outside of the classroom, in real-life settings where they have a chance to make a difference in the lives of families and communities. Extension programs, for their part, can be enriched by the energy, creativity, and perspective that many college students can provide. Additionally, Brennan et al. (2007) mentioned that extension plays a vital role in engaging youth through interactions with the local community. Youth can actively contribute to a variety of Extension activities that enhance local life. If youth are included in programs to meet the needs and empower communities, they can become lifelong participants and take on a sense of ownership in development efforts.

Furthermore, community service provides an avenue for the students to serve the community, apply what they have learned from the school, and in return, learn through their experiences. Schmiesing et al. (2005) pointed out that the volunteers’ experience in community service has significant benefits that include stronger social networks, healthier lifestyles, improved interpersonal relationships as well as improved self-confidence, self-esteem, and working relationships with others. Other studies have

described benefits as learned leadership skills that include networking, listening, communication, problem-solving, and collaboration skills (Singletary et al., 2005). Furthermore, the study of Diem and Nikola (2005) informed that community service experiences teach volunteers the interpersonal and group relational skills needed to become effective community leaders.

Indeed, studies have proven the benefits of engaging students with community service. However, the researcher would like to investigate further how it would help in the attainment of the “total development of man based on faith, science, and virtue” – the philosophy of RCC. Since college students are highly encouraged to engage in community service, this should have direct significance in the achievement of the reason why RCC exists. The experiences and the learning that the students gained through their engagement with this endeavor are worthwhile information that would help the researcher investigate its relevance to the achievement of school philosophy.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 shows the paradigm of the study in an input-process-output model. The *input* includes the survey of the community service engagement of the students during their college education in RCC. The community engagement or involvement of the students may be through the spearheaded activities of the CESO in its eight (8) programs, namely: community organization, health and sanitation, education and values formation, livelihood, social and cultural, environment and cleanliness, sports and recreation, and research (CESO Manual, 2017). This may also be through their involvement in the community service activities spearheaded by the recognized student organizations in RCC like the Youth Community Service Club (YCSC), Student Catholic Action (SCA), Supreme Student Council (SSC), Department Student Council (DSC), and other organizations outside the school that are aligned with the eight (8) programs of the CESO. The input also includes the survey on the impact of the community service engagement of the students in their learning and development in terms of faith, science, and virtue – the philosophy of RCC.

The *process* includes the data analysis of the quantitative data through the use of statistical software to determine the learning and development of the students through their engagement in community service toward the attainment of faith, science, and virtue.

The *output* includes the students’ learning in the conduct of community service, and their development toward achieving RCC’s philosophy in terms of faith, science, and virtue.

Figure 1. *Impact of Engagement with Community Service on the Student's Learning and Development Toward Achievement of RCC's Philosophy*

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the impact of engagement with community service on students' learning and development toward achieving RCC's philosophy of faith, science, and virtue. Specifically, it sought to:

1. Describe the participants' community service activities;
2. Describe the participants' learning with their engagement in community service; and
3. Determine the development of the participants in terms of faith, science, and virtue with their engagement in community service.

METHODOLOGY

This study made use of the descriptive-survey method of research to determine the students' community service activities, learning, and their assessment of how their development in terms of faith, science, and virtues was achieved. The participants of the study were 129 college graduates from batch 2019 and 100 college graduates from batch 2023 for a total of 229 participants. The batch 2019 is the last batch of graduates before the implementation of the K-12 curriculum in the Philippines and they are the last batch before the COVID-19 pandemic. The batch 2023 was the latest graduate of the college after the COVID-19 pandemic. The participants were composed of 158 or 69% females and 71 or 31% males with the majority of them in the programs of Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSEd), Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEEd), Bachelor of Science in Business Administration (BSBA), and Bachelor of Science in Civil Engineering (BSCE).
Table 1

Profile of the Respondents

Graduation Batch	f	%
Batch 2019	129	56.3
Batch 2023	100	43.7
Total	229	100.0
Sex	f	%
Male	158	69.0
Female	71	31.0
Total	229	100.0
Course	f	%
Bachelor of Arts in English Language (ABEL)	6	2.6
Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEEd)	38	16.6
Bachelor of Science in Accountancy (BSA)	13	5.7
BS Business Administration (BSBA)	44	19.2
BS Civil Engineering (BSCE)	31	13.5
Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSEd)	75	32.8
BS Hospitality Management (BSHM)	11	5
BS Information Technology (BSIT)	5	2.2
BS Tourism Management (BSTM)	6	2.6
Total	229	100.0

The instrument used in this study was a researcher-made questionnaire. It was subjected to content validation by the Research Director, Vice President for Academic Affairs, and Dean of one of the higher educational institutions in Angeles City. Before the data gathering, the questionnaire was pilot-tested to 30 students. The questionnaire was composed of three (3) parts: Part 1 was about the details of community service participated and or conducted by the students; Part 2 was about the learning of the students in the conduct of community service which was composed of ten items answerable using a 4-point scale of Strongly Agree (4), Agree (3), Disagree (2), and Strongly Disagree (1); and Part 3 was about the development of the students based on faith (5 items), science (5 items), and virtue (5 items) answerable using a 5-point scale of to a Very Great Extent (5), to a Great Extent (4), to a Moderate Extent (3), to a Slight Extent (2), and Not at All (1).

The frequency (f), percentage (%), rank, and mean (\bar{x}) values were used in the analyses and interpretations of data. To facilitate the interpretation of the mean (\bar{x}) score of the responses, the following were adopted:

Description of students' learning

Mean*	Descriptive Interpretation
1.00 – 1.49	Strongly Disagree
1.50 – 2.49	Disagree
2.50 – 3.49	Agree

3.50 – 4.00 Strongly Agree

Description of students' development in faith, science, and virtue

Mean*	Description
1.00 – 1.49	Not at All
1.50 – 2.49	to a Slight Extent
2.50 – 3.49	to a Moderate Extent
3.50 – 4.49	to a Great Extent
4.50 – 5.00	to a Very Great Extent

* based on the rule of rounding off of numbers

RESULTS

The data gathered were organized and processed using the appropriate statistical tools and techniques which revealed the following results:

Students Community Service Activities

The type of community service activities participated by the students are presented in Table 2. The result showed that the social and cultural ranked first among the community service where the students were commonly engaged followed by education and values formation (ranked 2), health and sanitation (ranked 3), and environment and cleanliness (ranked 4). The students were also engaged in community service activities related to sports and recreation, community organization, livelihood, and research.

Table 2

Rank Distribution of the Community Service Activities of the Participants

Type of Community Service Activities	f	Rank
Community Organization	140	6
Health and Sanitation	360	3
Education and Values Formation	385	2
Livelihood	120	7
Social and Cultural	460	1
Environment and Cleanliness	230	4
Sports and Recreation	180	5
Research	68	8

Learning in the Conduct of Community Service

Table 3 presents the learning of the participants through their engagement with community service activities. The results revealed that they strongly agree that their engagement with community service activities opened their eyes to the conditions of people in society ($\bar{x} = 3.87$); they gained a better understanding of the needs of others ($\bar{x} = 3.86$); they realized that they were more blessed than others ($\bar{x} = 3.86$); they were inspired and motivated to continuously improve their life ($\bar{x} = 3.83$); they gained a better understanding of people ($\bar{x} = 3.82$); encouraged doing more community service to other people ($\bar{x} = 3.79$); they felt the true feeling of happiness ($\bar{x} = 3.78$); they have gained a better understanding of themselves ($\bar{x} = 3.73$); they gained life skills that they will use in the future ($\bar{x} = 3.71$); and they have been able to apply their academic learning in a practical setting ($\bar{x} = 3.69$).

Table 3

Mean Distribution of Participants' Learning in the Conduct of Community Service

<i>Through engagement in community service</i>	Mean	Description
1. I have gained a better understanding of people.	3.82	Strongly Agree
2. I have gained a better understanding of myself.	3.73	Strongly Agree
3. I have gained a better understanding of the needs of others.	3.86	Strongly Agree
4. I have gained life skills that I will use in the future.	3.71	Strongly Agree
5. I have been able to apply my academic learning in a practical setting.	3.69	Strongly Agree
6. I realized that I am more blessed than others.	3.86	Strongly Agree
7. I felt the true feeling of happiness.	3.78	Strongly Agree
8. I encouraged doing more community service to other people.	3.79	Strongly Agree
9. I was inspired and motivated to continuously improve my life.	3.83	Strongly Agree
10. It opened my eyes to the conditions of people in society.	3.87	Strongly Agree
Overall mean	3.80	Strongly Agree

N=229; SD = Strongly Disagree (1.00-1.49), D = Disagree (1.50-2.49), A = Agree (2.50-3.49), SA = Strongly Agree (3.50-4.009)

Development of the Participants in terms of Faith, Science, and Virtue through Engagement with Community Service Activities

Table 4 presents the participants' development in terms of Faith, Science, and Virtue through engagement with community service activities. On *faith*, the results showed that the students strengthened to a very great extent their faith in God ($\bar{x} = 4.76$); they realized to a very great extent their responsibility of being in service to other people especially those who are in need ($\bar{x} = 4.75$); they developed to a very great extent to uphold truth, peace, justice and solidarity by respecting gender, cultural, religious and political differences ($\bar{x} = 4.71$); they became aware of the socio-economic, political, cultural and moral aspects of the society thus enabling them to organize and lead activities that contribute meaningfully to the progress and development of the environment and the community ($\bar{x} = 4.64$); and they acquired to a very great extent the knowledge, skills and proper attitude in analyzing, planning, monitoring, and evaluating outreach projects ($\bar{x} = 4.61$). In general, through the students' engagement with community service, they developed to a very great extent ($\bar{x} = 4.69$) the values of faith in the philosophy of RCC.

On *science*, the participants rated four indicators to a very great extent. They have developed a positive attitude in performing their tasks satisfactorily ($\bar{x} = 4.63$); they have developed their skills of communicating with people in a way that earns their respect and trust, thereby encouraging a cooperative and productive workplace that is conducive to the achievements of professional or assigned goals ($\bar{x} = 4.59$); they have critically contemplated problems and issues and think of solutions that contribute to a better understanding of the community ($\bar{x} = 4.53$); and they have developed critical, analytical, and creative thinking in meeting current and emerging needs of society ($\bar{x} = 4.50$). However, the participants have developed to a great extent their proficiency in linguistic competence and communicative performance ($\bar{x} = 4.41$). In general, through the students' engagement with community service, they developed to a very great extent ($\bar{x} = 4.53$) the values of science in the philosophy of RCC.

The third indicator of the school's philosophy is *virtue*. The result showed a rating of "to a very great extent" in all indicators of the development of the virtue through their engagement with community service activities. To a very great extent, the participants claimed that they have developed a respect for others regardless of their status in life ($\bar{x} = 4.77$); they have developed the willingness to take risks in initiating a meaningful change ($\bar{x} = 4.66$); they have developed their skills in working effectively with other people ($\bar{x} = 4.62$); they have developed the habit of active participation in providing community service, particularly to the underserved members of society ($\bar{x} = 4.61$); and they have strived to be a leader upholding universal values seeking to serve rather than to be served ($\bar{x} = 4.54$). In general, through the students' engagement with community service, they have developed to a very great extent ($\bar{x} = 4.64$) the values of virtue in the philosophy of RCC.

In general, the development of the participants through their engagement with community service activities was achieved to a very great extent the faith ($\bar{x} = 4.69$), science ($\bar{x} = 4.53$), and virtue ($\bar{x} = 4.64$) with an overall mean of 4.62.

Table 4

Mean Distribution of Participants' Development in terms of Faith, Science, and Virtue through their Engagement Community Service Activities

FAITH	Mean	Description
1. I have strengthened my faith in God.	4.76	To a Very Great Extent
2. I have realized my responsibility of being in service to other people especially those who are in need.	4.75	To a Very Great Extent
3. I became aware of the socio-economic, political, cultural, and moral aspects of the society thus enabling me to organize and lead activities that contribute meaningfully to the progress and development of the environment and the community.	4.64	To a Very Great Extent
4. I have acquired knowledge, skills, and a proper attitude in analyzing, planning, monitoring, and evaluating outreach projects.	4.61	To a Very Great Extent

Table 4 (Continuation)

FAITH	Mean	Description
5. I have developed to uphold truth, peace, justice, and solidarity by respecting gender, cultural, religious, and political differences.	4.71	To a Very Great Extent
<i>Sub-mean</i>	4.69	To a Very Great Extent
SCIENCE	Mean	Description
1. I have developed critical, analytical, and creative thinking in meeting the current and emerging needs of society.	4.50	To a Very Great Extent
2. I have developed proficiency in linguistic competence and communicative performance;	4.41	To a Great Extent
3. I have critically contemplated problems and issues, and think of solutions that contribute to a better understanding of the community.	4.53	To a Very Great Extent
4. I have developed my skills of communicating with people in a way that earns their respect and trust, thereby	4.59	To a Very Great Extent

encouraging a cooperative and productive workplace that is conducive to the achievement of professional or assigned goals.		
5. I have developed a positive attitude in performing my tasks satisfactorily.	4.63	To a Very Great Extent
	<i>Sub-mean</i>	To a Very Great Extent
	4.53	To a Very Great Extent
VIRTUE	Mean	Description
1. I have strived to be a leader upholding universal values seeking to serve rather than to be served.	4.54	To a Very Great Extent
2. I have developed my skills in working effectively with other people.	4.62	To a Very Great Extent
3. I have developed respect for others regardless of their status in life.	4.77	To a Very Great Extent
4. I have developed the willingness to take risks in initiating a meaningful change.	4.66	To a Very Great Extent
5. I have developed the habit of active participation in providing community service, particularly to the underserved members of society.	4.61	To a Very Great Extent
	<i>Sub-mean</i>	To a Very Great Extent
	4.64	To a Very Great Extent
	<i>Overall mean</i>	To a Very Great Extent
	4.62	To a Very Great Extent

N=229; Not at All (1.00-1.49), to a Slight Extent (1.50-2.49), to a Moderate Extent (2.50-3.49), to a Great Extent (3.50-4.49), to a Very Great Extent (4.50-5.00)

DISCUSSION

Students Community Service Activities

The social and cultural is the rank 1 among the community service programs where the students are engaged. Among the community service activities in this program is the cultural night presentation dubbed as the College Night for a Cause where the proceeds of the activity are allocated for the *Pamaskong Handog* – a gift-giving activity to the partner communities of RCC. This is a yearly activity in the college where the students are highly encouraged to participate in cultural affairs to gather funds for community service. The donations of the students for the victims of calamities like typhoons, volcanic eruptions, earthquakes, and those who were greatly affected by the COVID-19 pandemic were included in this program. Second in the rank among the community service activities participated by the students is the education and values formation. This includes the *tulung-dunong* program – where the college education students conducted reading, writing, and arithmetic tutorials to the pupils studying in the RCC-Sitio Babo Munting Paaralan and Inararo Learning Center. This is a year-long community service activity

where the students taking Bachelor of Elementary Education and Bachelor of Secondary Education are given a schedule to render tutorials and teaching activities to the pupils in the partner communities of RCC – the Sitio Babo, and Inararo. The college students also participated in the health and sanitation service to the community. This includes their participation in giving training to the residents, particularly to the children on proper toothbrushing, handwashing, and bathing. The distribution of slippers, soap, toothbrush, toothpaste, and other hygiene kits are included in this activity. In addition, since the RCC and partner organizations have constructed several toilets in the community, the students also provided training to the children on the proper utilization of the toilets.

Learning with the Engagement of Community Service Activities

The students who are engaged in community service strongly agree that it opens their eyes to the conditions of people in society. This is probably the fundamental learning that the participants may get through engagement with community service. They will become aware of the real-life situation of the people which will lead to their participation in community service activities. This strengthens the strategy of the Student Awareness Generates Action (SAGA) of Florida Southern College (2008), where they make the students aware of community issues through community service and such awareness leads to their involvement in the community through volunteerism and service. The students also confirm that their participation in community programs heightens their awareness of individuals who are less fortunate and helps them gain an appreciation for helping individuals in need. Furthermore, the students are more inspired and motivated to continuously improve their lives and they experience the true feeling of happiness. These results corroborate the findings of Hairston (2004) that through community service the delegates recognized the positive feelings of helping others, Bringle and Hatcher, (1995, as cited in Carlisle et al., 2020) that community engagement deepens the awareness of civic responsibility, Eyler and Giles (1999, as cited in Afzal & Hussain, 2020) that community service improves social skills, and Diem and Nikola (2005) that community service experiences teach volunteers the interpersonal and group relational skills needed to become effective community leaders.

Development of the Students in terms of Faith, Science, and Virtue through Engagement with Community Service Activities

The study shows the participants' development in terms of Faith, Science, and Virtue through engagement in community service activities. The results clearly emphasize the extent of the development of the students in terms of faith through their engagement with community service activities. They can strengthen their faith in God and realize their responsibility of being in service to other people especially those who are in need. The result indicates that the respondents' sense of empathy and sympathy for others has been positively developed. Through community service, the students develop a greater awareness of the situations of the people in the community. This fosters volunteers' sense of caring for others. As Perry and Katula (2001) found out, community service engagement is positively associated with efficacy, self-confidence, and feelings of responsibility for the well-being of others. Accordingly, Scales et al. (2001) stated that

through students' participation in community service learning, they manifested greater concern for the welfare of other persons and they sustained it throughout their studies than students without community service learning.

In addition, the results show that the philosophy of RCC in terms of science has been greatly developed with the college students through their engagement in community service activities. This shows that the respondents' knowledge in performing their tasks satisfactorily, skills in communicating with people, providing solutions to the problems of the community, and proficiency in linguistic competence and academic performance have been greatly developed. As *science* in the context of the philosophy of RCC refers to the constant search for knowledge and pursuit of academic excellence, the result is indicative that this context has been achieved through community service. Since community service is a social activity, the students' interactions with people provide them with experiences that they can use in the pursuit of academic excellence. Soria et al. (2012) mentioned that community service as a programmatic and intentional activity has the potential to impact both the social and academic domains of the experiences of college students. Students can use their learning from their experiences and integrate their new-found knowledge into their academic pursuits. In turn, community service helps students develop a connection between theory-driven academic studies and foster connections to real-life practice. Furthermore, Astin et al. (2000) in their longitudinal study in higher education, provide evidence that community service has positive effects on the cognitive and psychosocial development of the students, thus it positively contributes to their academic performance.

The third indicator of the school's philosophy is *virtue*. The participants rated all indicators to a very great extent on their development. This showed that the participants have greatly developed their respect for others regardless of their status in life; have the habit of actively participating in providing community service, particularly to the underserved members of society; and strive to be leaders upholding universal values seeking to serve rather than to be served. As *virtue* in the context of the philosophy of RCC refers "to our conviction that since we are inherently good, we can develop moral values through strong determination and perseverance," the result indicates that students' participation in community service activities achieved this purpose. Community service is service done for the benefit of other people for free. This requires determination and perseverance to help others considering the risks and untoward situations in the community. Persevering to participate in community service is a reflection of the personal character of the volunteers that are aligned with moral values and proper behavior. According to Weider (2005), the character and moral development of students is of immense interest to educators, and how community service can impact this development since it cannot be ascribed to ethics class alone. Boss (1994, cited in Weider 2005) found that the student's moral reasoning ability improves when students engage in community service. She further discovered that the students who engaged in community service projects with problem-solving activities that included moral issues enhanced the moral development of the students to the greatest.

In general, the result reveals that the philosophy of RCC which is a total development of man based on faith, science, and virtue is achieved to a very great extent

through the engagement of the students with community service activities. The RCC students who are engaged in community service strengthen their *faith* in God and believe in themselves that they can live moral lives by being of service to other people especially those who are in need. The *science* which is a constant search for knowledge and pursuit of academic excellence is inculcated in the students through engagement with service-learning activities like education and values formation, health and sanitation, community research, and the like that have proven significance to strengthen students' understanding in subject matter or course content (Mahoney & Schamber, 2011, as cited in Kingston et al., 2014; Smith, 2021), which led to improved academic performance of the students (Afzal & Hussain, 2020; Parlier et al., 2022; Wood & Harris, 2015). Further, the result reveals that the third indicator of RCC Philosophy which is *virtue* is also achieved to a very great extent through the students' engagement with community service activities. The conviction that the students are inherently good is manifested through giving service and helping others for free exemplifying their moral values and development.

Based on the foregoing, the results provide significant information that the engagement of the RCC college students with community service activities helps to a very great extent the achievement of the philosophy of RCC which is a "total development of man based on faith, science, and virtue." The results also prove that community service as an educational requirement has direct significance in the achievement of the reason why RCC exists – its philosophy. Thus, through engagement with community service, the RCCians can be greatly developed to become well-rounded graduates based on Faith, Science, and Virtue.

Conclusions

Based on the foregoing, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The college students of RCC are mostly engaged in community service activities in terms of social and cultural, education and values formation, health and sanitation, environment and cleanliness, and sports and recreation while they are less engaged in community organization, livelihood, and research.
2. The students strongly agree that engagement in community service activities opens their eyes to the conditions of people in society, they gain a better understanding of the needs of others, they realize that they are more blessed than others, they are inspired and motivated to continuously improve their life, and they gain a better understanding of people.
3. Through the students' engagement in community service activities, their development based on faith, science, and virtue is achieved to a very great extent. This demonstrates their characteristics as true RCCians.

Recommendations

1. The engagement of the students with community service activities has been found instrumental in the achievement of the philosophy of RCC which is a total development of man based on Faith, Science, and Virtue, thus it is hereby recommended that the engagement of the college students with community service activities should be strengthened and sustained.
2. The Community Extension Service Office of RCC and other organizations should provide more activities related to community organization, livelihood, and research to improve the participation of the students in these programs.
3. For future research, explore the correlation of the length of engagement and type of community service activities of the students to their learning and development.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study was supported by the Office of Community Extension Service Office of Republic Central Colleges. The author declares that he has no conflicts of interest. All procedures performed involving humans were under the ethical standards of the RCC Ethics Board. Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants involved in the study. Plagiarism was strictly avoided, there was no bias in the interpretation of the results, and the data was used purely for research.

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